

PROMOTING A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE AMONG STUDENTS IS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses health, healthy lifestyle, physical education, factors of physical development, and the role of physical education in the upbringing of a harmoniously developed generation. A scientific study of the attitudes of young people to a healthy lifestyle also provides conclusions and recommendations.

KEYWORDS: *Health, Healthy Lifestyle, Physical Education, Physical Development, Factor, Physical Education, Exercise, Diet, Sleep, Hygiene.*

INTRODUCTION

Health is a balanced unit of biological, mental, physical conditions and labor activity of the human body. Health is happiness for everyone. Its labor productivity is a necessary condition for the development of the country's economic power and the welfare of the people. A conscious and responsible approach to public health should be the norm of life and morality of society and all its members.

The key to good health is physical activity. Abu Ali Ibn Sina teaches the need to focus on seven things in a healthy lifestyle (STT) and health care. These include:

- Customer Moderation,
 - Choice Of Food To Eat And Drink,
 - Cleaning The Body From Debris,
 - Maintain Proper Structure;
 - Adequate And Good Nasal Air Intake,
 - Pay Attention To Clothing,
 - Regulation of Physical and Mental activity (this includes sleep and wakefulness.) While our ancestor Abu Ali ibn Sina predicted that all diseases that could be treated without surgery would come and be treated only by movement, the Russian anatomist, physician, and pedagogue LF Lesgaft classified exercise as 4th century BC and expressed its effects on the human body in poetic lines.
 - A healthy lifestyle (STL) includes increasing a person's cultural and physical development, productivity, and creativity. The main components of STT are effective work, personal hygiene, and avoidance of bad habits, and proper nutrition at the appointed time, physical
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training, regular physical activity. STT is one of the main measures in the prevention of diseases.

- STT- allows you to meet a certain amount of mental and physical requirements to a satisfactory level. There are more and more types of fitness: exercise, diet, sleep, bathing, and more.
- Everything should be aimed at one goal - to improve people's health. While our main goal today is to scientifically substantiate the role of physical education in the upbringing of a harmoniously developed generation, it is worth mentioning the following:
- Development of special theoretical knowledge and practical skills in healthy lifestyles among young people.
- Educating young people about a healthy lifestyle and its main components, - Conducting surveys among physical education specialists in the upbringing of a harmoniously developed generation.

In order to complete the above tasks, we conducted a survey on physical activity of students. Two 6th grade students of the secondary school took part in the survey. There were a total of 45 students, including 25 girls and 20 boys. During the survey, the questions were structured as follows and the answers were collected. S O 'R O V N O M A (questions)

- What do you mean by physical education?
- Do you exercise?
- Do you like physical education?
- Do you want to exercise?
- Is physical training easy or difficult?
- Do you consider physical education as a basic science?
- According to the results of the survey:
- What do you mean by physical education?

When it comes to physical education, girls are more likely to respond than boys.

Do you do physical training?

When asked if they do physical activity, 16 out of 20 boys answered "Yes" and 13 out of girls.

Do you like physical education?

When asked if they liked physical education, 18 boys and 20 girls said yes.

Would you like to get some exercise?

When asked if they wanted to exercise, 17 boys and 22 girls said yes.

Is physical training easy or difficult?

When asked if physical education is easy or difficult, all boys said yes, and 22 girls said yes.

Do you consider physical education as a basic science?

When asked if physical education is the main subject, 15 boys and 17 girls answered "Yes".

The results of the study showed that it was found that students view physical education as a secondary task. But we must not forget that physical education is a key factor in all aspects.

Summarizing the data, we obtained the following statistics:

Number 1 Question Positive Answers% Question 2 Positive Answers% Question 3 Positive Answers% Question 4 Positive Answers% Question 5 Positive Answers% Question 6 Positive Answers%

Participants :	Number	Question 1	Positive answers %	Question 2	Positive answers %	Question 3	Positive answers %	Question 4	Positive answers %	Question 5	Positive answers %	Question 6	Positive answers %
Jami	45	45											
Boys	20	11	24%	16	36%	18	40%	17	38%	20	44%	15	33%
Girls	25	23	51%	13	29%	20	44%	22	49%	22	49%	17	38%
Total% indicator	100	34	75%	29	65%	38	84%	39	87%	42	93%	32	71%

In conclusion, in order to raise a healthy generation, it is necessary to engage in regular physical activity in order to maintain good health.

In order to educate young people in a healthy way, first of all, it is necessary to form a healthy lifestyle.

In the upbringing of a harmoniously developed generation, it is necessary to use hygienic factors wisely to increase physical activity.

REFERENCES:

1. Azimov I, Sobitov SH "Physiology of sports" Tashkent -1993
2. Axmedoa N.K. "Atlas of human anatomy" Tashkent - 2006
3. Ashmarin B. A and others "Theory and methods of physical education" M. Enlightenment 1990s
4. Weinbaum YAS "Physical Education Hygiene" Tashkent "Teacher" 1988
5. Goncharova OV "Development of physical abilities of young athletes" Tashkent 2005
6. D.J. SHaripova, G.S. Fuzailova, G.A. SHaxmurova, M.T. Toirova, M. Turkmenova, D. Zufarova "Formation of a healthy lifestyle in students" Fergana 2010
7. A. A. Sarukhanov, *Sovremennye problem organizatsiizanyatiypofizicheskoykulture v Vuze so studentamispetsialnoy...* Innovations in pedagogy and psychology, 2020
8. SultanovaNurkhonAnvarovna, The importance of didactic games in the activities of primary school students. Continuous Education 1 (Special Issue), 42-46
9. Sultonova N.A.,

Teoreticheskieosnovypodgotovkidetey V Sovremennyxusloviyax K Sotsialnojizni V Seme, Scientific Progress 1 (6), 631-635.

9. Shavkatjon Son Nr Start Developing the Speech Of Mental Students In The Classroom //Research And Education. - 2022. - T. 1. – No. 1. - S. 263-267.
10. Hatamjono‘G‘Li H. I. Technologies for the Formation of the Skill of Creative Thinking in Weak Auditory Students //International Journal Of Social Science & Interdisciplinary Research Issn: 2277-3630 Impact Factor: 7.429. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 11. – C. 265-271.
11. Xonbabayev, S. H. "D.(2022). Socio-Pedagogical Basis Of Spiritual And Spiritual Education Mechanisms In Society And Foreign Experiences." International Journal Of Culture And Modernity: 285-292.